

Getting freshwater spatiotemporal data on track – towards the interoperability of freshwater-specific data

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Abstract

Spatiotemporal earth system data on freshwaters are poorly organized at present and their rich potential for research and environmental management is barely exploited. Part of this deficiency relates to the spatial structure of river networks, in particular, which requires a specialized workflow for earth system data integration and use. To address this challenge, we developed the GeoFRESH online platform, available at <http://geofresh.org/>. GeoFRESH provides the integration, processing, management and visualization of standardized spatiotemporal earth system data related to freshwaters on the global scale. Users can (i) upload point data; (ii) automatically assign the points to a new fine-scale hydrographical network; (iii) map the points to the corresponding upstream catchment; (iv) annotate the points with site-specific and upstream environmental information based on a suite of 104 layers capturing topography, climate, landcover and soil characteristics; (v) calculate network distances among points; and (vi) download the compiled data ready for downstream analyses. GeoFRESH capitalizes on open-source PostgreSQL, PostGIS and pgRouting software, building on a new database comprising the global 'Hydrography90m' stream network at 90 m resolution, comprising a total of 726 million unique stream segments. The platform is readily expandable thanks to its modular structure and serves as a key element in supporting freshwater science and management relying on high-resolution geospatial analyses. GeoFRESH thus contributes significantly to FAIR data management and exchange by enabling globally standardized stream network queries and offering a powerful tool to stakeholders engaged in water research, sustainable water management and the monitoring of freshwater ecosystem services alike.

I. Introduction

The central idea of the one-year pilot project was to support researchers in performing geospatial analyses in river ecosystems. Rivers are characterized by high connectivity within dendritic networks and strong fragmentation because of river intermittencies¹ and extensive damming². Integrating earth system data into freshwater research and management currently represents a major challenge given this specific spatial structure. Hence, any simple data overlay of, for example, land cover, climate or dams at a given stream reach position is likely to provide only a fraction of the potential dependencies between these environmental drivers and the freshwater environment³. This calls for a large-scale framework that enables routing environmental information through hydrographical networks to assess environmental impacts such as water pollution, high nutrient loadings, the disruption of connectivity by dams or weirs, or flow alteration including extreme flood and drought events. Spatially explicit data specifically tailored towards riverine ecosystems would substantially improve research analyses and scenario development for these systems⁴. Performing such analyses in river ecosystems requires advanced skills in using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and in the case of complex workflows, GIS programming skills. In addition, to ensure scalability of workflows and thus avoid computers to succumb to large data volumes, the choice of the software and tools is critical, often followed by a steep learning curve in acquainting to new languages/syntax.

Thus, the central challenges of the present pilot project were threefold: (i) simplify the user experience for all potential users, even when their technical geospatial knowledge is limited, (ii) enable data

processing within a central online hub rather than users' personal computers to enable the handling of large amounts of data, and (iii) ensure the functionality and data-handling capacity is scalable such that it could support workflows at large scale, if needed. Our proposed solution to addressing these challenges was to create an online platform where users can upload point data coordinates, annotate the point data with both local and upstream environmental data, calculate network distances among the uploaded points, and download the processed data for further downstream analyses or presentation.

II. Results

The result of the one-year pilot project is the GeoFRESH online platform, which is publicly available at <http://geofresh.org/>. The platform allows users to (i) upload point data, (ii) automatically assign the points to the hydrographical network, (iii) map the points along with information on the corresponding upstream catchment characteristics, (iv) annotate local and upstream environmental information to each point from a suite of 104 layers regarding topography, climate, landcover and soil characteristics, (v) calculate network distances among points, to finally (vi) download analysis-ready data to their local computer. The platform consists of an R Shiny⁵ interface with a (i) landing page and tabs to (ii) perform the analyses, (iii) follow a tutorial and (iv) read about the pilot project. The implemented PostgreSQL⁶/PostGIS⁷ software and pgRouting⁸ plugin operate as the technical backbone of the platform. In short, we transformed the recently developed Hydrography90m stream network⁹, comprising 726 million unique stream segments and corresponding sub-catchments into a PostgreSQL database along with routing information, such that each segment can be linked to its up- and downstream neighbours. All geospatial database layers are registered in IGB's geodata management system GeoNode¹⁰ (geo.igb-berlin.de), allowing to add metadata, create advanced map styles and add filter options. GeoNode delivers OGC web map services (WMS) and web feature services (WFS) for each of the layers that can be included in the map interface of the GeoFRESH platform. In addition, GeoFRESH relies on open-source spatial analysis tools like GDAL¹¹ and GRASS GIS¹² for data processing and mapping. The platform is hosted at the IGB and the publicly available code repository is hosted at <https://github.com/glowabio/geofresh>. GeoFRESH is licensed under the GNU General Public License v3.0.

The main innovation of GeoFRESH lies in the easy and non-technical support to perform geospatial analyses in river ecosystems, including catchment delineation and assessments of network connectivity. GeoFRESH does not require prior registration, nor is its use restricted to any geographic region worldwide. Consequently, the platform makes a major contribution to Open Science and the FAIR principles.

Welcome to the GeoFRESH platform

GeoFRESH is a platform that helps freshwater researchers to process point data across the global river network by providing a set of spatial tools.

Follow the demo or upload your csv-table that contains geographic coordinates. GeoFRESH allows you to

- map your points,
- move points to the nearest stream network segment,
- delineate upstream catchments of each point,
- extract a suite of environmental attributes across the catchment,
- and download the data for further analyses.

GeoFRESH is based on the Hydrography90m stream network. For more information, please see the [publication](#) and [hydrography.org](#) regarding the single data layers.

Analysis

Check out the different analysis steps.

Tutorial

Check out the full functionality of the platform.

Documentation

Learn about the project background.

NFDI4Earth

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IGB
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Figure 1 Screenshot of the GeoFRESH platform landing page, available at <http://geofresh.org/>.

The GeoFRESH platform includes a tutorial explaining the functionality of the platform step-by-step. While the analyses themselves is largely self-explanatory, users can switch between tabs and read the tutorial while performing the analysis.

Step by step guide to GeoFRESH

Upload your data

For this example, we will use a random subset of 100 occurrence points, drawn from the Harmonised freshwater fish occurrence and abundance data for 12 federal states in Germany, downloaded from GBIF.

Point data coordinates need to be uploaded as a comma-separated table (.csv) with the three columns ID, longitude and latitude (column names are flexible). Longitude and latitude coordinates are required to be in the WGS84 coordinate reference system.

The points are instantly visualized on the map.

Upload your data

Please provide your point data as a .csv table with three columns: a unique 'id', 'longitude', 'latitude'.
Coordinates should be provided in the WGS84 coordinate reference system. Column names are flexible. The number of points in your .csv file is currently limited to 1000, and upload file size should not exceed 1MB.

Point data (.csv format)

Browse... tutorial_points.csv
Upload complete
Load test data

Snapping method: sub-catchment (default)
Points will be snapped to the nearest location on the river segment of the sub-catchment the point falls in.
Snap points 0/0

id	longitude	latitude
409502932	7.2413	51.8129
4095618985	8.307	51.4865
4095456780	11.7058	51.6406
4095505290	11.2393	53.1557

Showing 1 to 4 of 100 entries

Map

- Sentinel-2 cloudless
- OpenStreetMap
- Input points
- Snapped points
- Stream segments
- Sub-catchments

Legend: input points (blue dot), Snapped points (red dot)

The points can also be overlaid with the stream segment map.

Figure 2 Screenshot of the GeoFRESH Tutorial page, showing the analysis workflow step-by-step.

The current implementation supports the following workflow:

- Users start by uploading their point data coordinates as a comma-separated table (.csv) with the three columns ID, longitude and latitude. Column names are flexible. Longitude and latitude coordinates are required to be in the WGS84 coordinate reference system. A progress bar allows monitoring the upload process. The table is instantly displayed and can be cross-checked and queried by the user prior to the next steps.

A test data set (national fish occurrence data¹³ from NFDI4Biodiversity) is made available to enable first-time users to explore the platform functionality without having to provide their own data.

- After the upload, the points need to be assigned to the corresponding sub-catchments and stream segments of the Hydrography90m dataset⁹. This assignment, called “point snapping”, moves any given point to the closest stream segment. In the default option, the closest stream segment is located within the sub-catchment the point lies in. The snapping procedure makes use of the PostGIS function ST_LineLocatePoint to find the location of the closest point on a line geometry to the given point. In addition, users can choose between the type of snapping: defining a distance threshold (in meters) between the point and the stream segment (i.e., only stream segments close to the point will be considered), or using flow accumulation as an additional criterion (i.e., size of the upstream catchment area). Flow accumulation allows users to specify whether the points should be snapped to small or large rivers.
- Once the points are assigned to the network, the map shows both the original (in blue) and snapped points (in red) overlaid on the sub-catchments. In addition, the calculated upstream catchments are displayed as raster files on the map. Users can thus cross-check whether the points were snapped correctly, whether the catchment delineations match expectations, or whether another type of snapping may be preferable.
- Users can annotate the point data with environmental information across the sub-catchment of each point. From a suite of 104 variables, there is a choice among a suite of 48 variables related to topography and hydrography, 19 current bioclimatic variables (1981-2010), 15 soil variables and 22 land cover variables of the most recent year. Multiple selections are possible. For each selected environmental variable, users will receive summary statistics (mean, minimum, maximum, range, standard deviation = sd) for each point location as a table, which can subsequently be downloaded (see below).
- Additionally, the summary statistics (mean, min, max, sd) for the upstream catchment of each point for each of the selected environmental variables is calculated and displayed in a table.
- Users can assess hydrographic network distances among the uploaded points and receive a distance matrix for download. This can be useful to assess point distances to dams, for example, or population patterns of species considering the particular network structure.
- Finally, users can download all data as multiple comma-separated tables within a single zip-file. All data are removed after closing the browser window and thus the session, so that no user data are permanently stored on the platform.

Analysis workflow

The GeoFRESH platform allows to upload point data, snap (move) the points to the stream network, query upstream environmental information, and download the resulting table.

Currently the platform includes 48 variables related to **topography and hydrography**, 19 **climate variables**, (i.e., current bioclimatic variables), 15 **soil** variables and 22 **land cover** variables.

For the uploaded points, you will obtain

- i) one table per environmental variable, where each row corresponds to one point, followed by the ID of the sub-catchment where the point falls into, and the summary statistics of the variable within this sub-catchment
- ii) a table including summary statistics for the upstream catchment of each point

In the case that variables were scaled in the raster layers, we have rescaled them back to their original values in the tables.

Upload your data

Please provide your point data as a .csv table with three columns: a unique 'id', 'longitude', 'latitude'.

Coordinates should be provided in the WGS84 coordinate reference system. Column names are flexible. The number of points in your .csv file is currently limited to 1000, and upload file size should not exceed 1MB.

Point data (.csv format)

Browse... tutorial_points.csv

Upload complete

Load test data

Snapping method: sub-catchment (default)
Points will be snapped to the nearest location on the river segment of the sub-catchment the point falls in.

Snap points

Step 6 of 6 completed 6 / 6

100%

Show 10 entries Search:

id	longitude	latitude	new longitude	new latitude	subcatchment id
4058503931	7.2413	51.8129	7.2413	51.812917	507804526
4058610695	8.307	51.4865	8.307	51.487083	508082108
4058496706	11.7058	51.8466	11.7062	51.8462	507777524
4058505990	11.2393	53.1557	11.239717	53.156117	506799932

Showing 1 to 10 of 100 entries Previous 1 2 3 4 5 ... 10 Next

Download

Figure 3 The analysis page allows users to upload their point data and assign (i.e., “snap”) the points to the Hydrography90m stream network. A progress bar serves to monitor the data processing.

Figure 4 Map showing uploaded and snapped points on top of the Hydrography90m sub-catchments, which constitute the basic spatial units implemented in the platform. Blue dots show the original points, and red dots represent the snapped ones that have been slightly moved such that they are assigned to a stream segment.

Select environmental variables

Select environmental variables

Activate the checkboxes to select the required environmental information that should be summarized within the upstream catchment of each point. Please see the source and the citation for each category under the 'Documentation' tab.

Topography	Climate	Soil	Landcover
<input type="checkbox"/> Mean elevation	<input type="checkbox"/> Annual Mean Temperature	<input type="checkbox"/> Derived saturated water content	<input type="checkbox"/> Cropland, rainfed
<input type="checkbox"/> Flow accumulation	<input type="checkbox"/> Mean Diurnal Range	<input type="checkbox"/> Clay content	<input type="checkbox"/> Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding
<input type="checkbox"/> Flow accumulation (positive values)	<input type="checkbox"/> Isothermality	<input type="checkbox"/> Sand content	<input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic cropland
<input type="checkbox"/> Cell maximum curvature	<input type="checkbox"/> Temperature Seasonality	<input type="checkbox"/> Silt content	<input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic natural vegetation
<input type="checkbox"/> Cell minimum curvature	<input type="checkbox"/> Max Temperature of Warmest Month	<input type="checkbox"/> Derived available soil water capacity	<input type="checkbox"/> Tree cover, broadleaved, evergreen
<input type="checkbox"/> Cell elevation difference	<input type="checkbox"/> Min Temperature of Coldest Month	<input type="checkbox"/> Soil organic carbon content	<input type="checkbox"/> Tree cover, broadleaved, deciduous
<input type="checkbox"/> Cell gradient	<input type="checkbox"/> Temperature Annual Range	<input type="checkbox"/> Soil pH x 10 in H2O	<input type="checkbox"/> Tree cover, needleleaved, evergreen
<input type="checkbox"/> Shortest distance to drainage divide	<input type="checkbox"/> Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter	<input type="checkbox"/> Bulk density	<input type="checkbox"/> Tree cover, needleleaved, deciduous
<input type="checkbox"/> Longest distance to drainage divide	<input type="checkbox"/> Mean Temperature of Driest Quarter	<input type="checkbox"/> Cation exchange capacity	<input type="checkbox"/> Tree cover, mixed leaf type
<input type="checkbox"/> Nearest down stream stream grid cell	<input type="checkbox"/> Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter	<input type="checkbox"/> Coarse fragments volumetric	<input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tree and shrub
<input type="checkbox"/> Outlet grid cell in the network	<input type="checkbox"/> Mean Temperature of Coldest Quarter	<input type="checkbox"/> Grade of a sub-soil being acid	<input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic herbaceous cover
<input type="checkbox"/> Down stream stream node grid cell	<input type="checkbox"/> Annual Precipitation	<input type="checkbox"/> Depth to bedrock (R horizon) up to 200 cm	<input type="checkbox"/> Shrubland
<input type="checkbox"/> Euclidean distance	<input type="checkbox"/> Precipitation of Wettest Month	<input type="checkbox"/> Probability of occurrence of R horizon	<input type="checkbox"/> Grassland

Figure 4 Users can annotate the uploaded points with local and upstream environmental information by using checkboxes to select from 104 layers: 48 variables related to topography and hydrography, 19 current bioclimatic variables (1981-2010), 15 soil variables and 22 land cover variables of the most recent year.

III. Challenges and Gaps

The available time frame of one year to design and build the platform from scratch proved sufficient to incorporate all critical elements, but it is obvious that there is potential for further development regarding additional data and functionalities (see below). The platform is built in a modular architecture, which facilitates expanding its functionalities, including features that may be requested by future users. User feedback can be directed to the Github issues page, available at <https://github.com/glowabio/geofresh/issues>.

A substantial amount of time was spent on testing the basic functions and the scalability of the PostgreSQL database. As we progressed from the development to the production version of the platform, we encountered a bottleneck in storage space when integrating the entire database with sub-catchment and stream segment geometries, as well as topography, climate, soil and landcover layers. Nevertheless, we expect to shortly integrate the (readily computed) climate and landcover time-series across the last decades missing so far to fully cover the temporal scale of the available data, for example to address any lag-effects in river ecosystems.

IV. Relevance for the community and NFDI4Earth

We expect the GeoFRESH platform to lower the hurdle for users to take advantage of geospatial freshwater-specific data processing and management. Given the usually complex GIS routines in assessing the connectivity and integration of environmental data in freshwater-specific workflows, GeoFRESH removes the burden by offering simple and yet powerful functionalities. This simple design will support stakeholders in scientific research, sustainable water management and monitoring of freshwater ecosystem services alike, offering instant data extraction and analyses at any given location on Earth. We expect the research community of freshwater earth system (NFDI4Earth) and biodiversity sciences (NFDI4Biodiversity) to become key users, where GeoFRESH will facilitate exploring impacts of climate or landcover change and a broad range of drivers on water quality and quantity, species occurrences, and more. Moreover, we expect that with the data release of the [Surface Water and Ocean Topography \(SWOT\)](#) mission by NASA (surface freshwater estimates at 100 m resolution every 21 days), the demand for freshwater-specific data that are interoperable will greatly increase. Despite its character as a pilot project, the GeoFRESH platform provides a critical stepping stone in this direction. Currently, we prepare a peer-reviewed publication describing the GeoFRESH platform and will also showcase it during conferences and workshops to raise awareness of its large potential within the scientific community.

V. Future Directions

The current version of the GeoFRESH platform provides the key elements needed for geospatial freshwater-specific workflows. In terms of the further development of the platform, we intend to integrate:

- extended point snapping functionalities (e.g. set stream order)

- manual editing regarding the spatial location of points
- lakes into the hydrographic network
- the interoperability of the *hydrographr* R-package

Our long-term perspective is to ensure sufficient funding to maintain and further develop GeoFRESH, while simultaneously exploring possibilities to combine the idea of GeoFRESH with a blueprint of, for example, the Virtual Research Environments in aquatic research, which is developed within the EU AqualNFRA project (www.aquainfra.eu).

The GeoFRESH platform is a first step towards facilitating freshwater geospatial analyses, and thus removing redundancies in the management and processing of (big) freshwater geospatial and environmental data. This will be a central feature in providing support to the scientific community, especially in view of the massive amounts of spatial high-resolution data on river networks, which require efficient and targeted processing workflows designed to analyse dendritic networks, which are not necessarily part of the general skill portfolio of aquatic scientists and water managers.

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